

Preventing Animal Cruelty in the Name of Textile and Fashion

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Abstract:- Every living thing, including animals, has the right to exist as fully as possible. In addition to the significance of humans to the environment, it is also impossible to ignore the importance of wildlife. The significance of living organisms resides in the fact that they are responsible for maintaining the natural equilibrium in concert with nature. If we are discussing humans, we must acknowledge that both (Animals & Humans) are vital and that they make every effort to defend themselves from the changing environment and other elements. According to what we have learned from studying history, ancient people either kill animals or wore animal skins for protection. In the past, man lacked education and had no other resources, so he had no choice but to slaughter and wear animal skins. Modern man is educated and has many options for covering his body, but he still kills animals in the name of clothing and fashion. This is due to the fact that modern men use shortcuts to enhance their beauty. In this article of the paper, we will discuss how to put an end to animal cruelty in the textile and apparel industries. How can we obtain products that are beneficial to both the environment and animals without harming them?

Keywords:- Environmentally Friendly, Wildlife Conservation, Bio Degradable, Sustainability, Eco-Friendly, Textile, Fashion.

I. INTRODUCTION

As I have basically outlined, all living things in the natural world, including human beings, have the same fundamental rights to the ability to live and breathe as we do. The modern human being has attained such a high level of education that he believes he is the all-powerful God of the universe. Because of man's incredible level of advancement, even the most challenging endeavours are now within his reach. Our technology has advanced to the point where it is currently researching the subject of how it can keep a person living after they have passed away. In our classes, we cover a wide range of topics, including Hindi, English, Science, Biology, Chemistry, Physics, and Social Science, amongst others. Now you are all saying that we are talking about trying to prevent cruelty to animals in the name of textile and fashion, and then how humans, animals, and certain kinds of study subjects have become involved in this by looking at the subject of reading. This is what you are saying. I would like to respond to all of you with this illustration that we have all read and heard before, which is that if we cause damage to nature or the environment, then

nature or the environment will also retaliate, also known as "tit for tat." Balance in nature/environment is important. The modern human being does not want to put in a lot of effort, and because of this, society has become increasingly harsh. In the same way that a mind without any thoughts is the home of the demon, a lack of effort in our work also leads to an increase in cruel behaviour?

According to what we have learned from studying history, when the species of human beings first appeared on Earth, the first humans did not have any sort of sense of humour or understanding. Furthermore, they did not have any sort of living and any sort of slick, as if they did not know who they were. They are unable to safeguard themselves from the many different kinds of natural occurrences that can occur in the environment, such as changes in temperature, natural disasters, storms, aquatic animals, and so on.

Then gradually, they invented new ways to survive the harsh conditions. At that time, he began wearing only the bark of trees and the leaves of plants as clothes; however, this changed as a result of changes in nature and the environment, such as the cold. The bark and leaves of plants were not sufficient to protect against heat, sun, shade, rain, storm, wild animals, and other hazards. As a consequence, he gradually began killing creatures for their skin. After that, they began to protect themselves from the severe weather by dressing in the skins of recently deceased animals, which they wore as clothing. because the heat generated by the dead creatures' skin could be used to keep the human body warm. During that time period, humans did not have access to the same level of education that would have allowed them to understand that they were killing animals for their own advantage, which is now considered to be an act of animal cruelty. It's not that he didn't care; he was upset that he was being cruel. However, in today's world, people still torture and kill animals in the name of the textile and apparel industries. Animals are subjected to such severe cruelty in the fashion industry that by the time they are released they are neither alive nor deceased. How tragic it is that the materials for our pricey clothing and expensive fashions come from a living organism that is, in every respect, the same as a human being. Leather is primarily crafted from the hides of various animals. Fabrics, clothing, and various leather fashion accoutrements such as leather shoes, belts, wallets, watch straps, and a great deal more are included in this category. In a similar manner, the hair from certain creatures is utilized not only in the production of textiles and clothing, but also in the fashion industry. The soft, attractive

feathers of birds are used to make pillows, which are then used to decorate the walls of our homes. Additionally, in the name of fashion, animal replicas are also used to decorate the walls of our homes. This is what the industry refers to as fashion. We have no choice but to make use of the products that are manufactured in our homes using various components derived from animals, birds, and other forms of life, including the animal and avian skins, feathers, and fur that are woven into textiles and fashioned into garments for human consumption. In addition, animals are killed for the apparel industry.

Animals are subjected to a variety of tests in the textile and fashion industries so that people can safely use beauty products for themselves without causing any damage to the animals. For instance, some animals are slaughtered so that fat can be extracted and obtained from a specific portion of their body. This fat is then used as a source for the production of glycerine. Beautiful coats and other accessories are also produced in the name of fashion, including fur coats, jackets, and other items worn by animal hair. However, we are obligated to practice fashion in the name of aesthetics, regardless of the price we pay for that fashion. They are created with the goal of appealing to fashion. It would take too much time to mention all of the different products that are manufactured by cruelly murdering animals in the name of clothing and fashion if we were to list them all here. There are many different kinds of these products. I have something important to discuss with you, and that is how we can put an end to the cruel treatment of animals and birds that is associated with the clothing and apparel industries. The first thing we need to do is raise people's awareness. Many people maintain various wild species as pets. These pets can be any kind of wild animals, such as a tiger, panther, dog, wolf, wild cat, goat, sheep, buffalo, cow, etc., and there are many other kinds of pet animals. Injury, illness, or removal from their natural environment are typically the driving forces behind the domestication of these creatures. All of these animals, such as cheetahs, lions, leopards, and other types of wild animals, but animals that cannot survive in the jungle in some different circumstances are referred to as pets. This is because they cannot survive in the jungle in their natural environments. It is necessary to clip such animals' body hair whenever their environment or living circumstances are altered, as is the case when they are kept as pets, in sanctuaries, or zoos. This makes it necessary for such animals to have their body hair trimmed.

The quality of the cleaning and grooming care that other animals, including humans, require is analogous to what is expected of them in this regard. For us to be able to make contact with woodland guards, pet keepers, old age keepers, and caretakers of animal shelters to receive assistance from them, it is important for us to cut or trim their hair, nails, and horns according to other seasons during this time. In addition, it is necessary for us to do so to comply with other seasons. Because they maintain a healthy equilibrium of loving emotions with all of the animals, birds, and other creatures that are in their environment, and because they watch out for one another. As a result of this,

there is a growing trust among the animals that this human will not in any way cause us any harm. If this is the case, then the animal does not in any way represent a threat to the person who is being talked about. It is common knowledge that cutting or trimming the hair of certain animals does not cause them any harm, and it is also essential to the overall health of the animals that they have their hair trimmed regularly because it is one of the factors that contribute to the overall health of the animals. In addition to everything mentioned above, we also have the choice to solicit the assistance of volunteers. It is also within our capabilities to acquire animal hairs without inflicting any kind of harm on the creatures concerned. To achieve this goal, we need to increase people's awareness of this problem while also educating them on how we can acquire animal products that are not harmful to the environment. Human hair is also used in the production of hairstyles, and in the same way that animal hair is used in the manufacturing of clothing, human hair can be used to create clothing that has the appearance of being made of fur. There are many kinds of hair, including animal hair and human hair, and the functionality of each form of hair inspires us to make a variety of products. For instance, human hair and animal hair are not the same, but human hair itself can come in a variety of textures and colours. Because of these different permutations, we can create clothing that is appropriate for a wide range of settings. This will not have any negative effect whatsoever on either the animals or the task at hand; in fact, both the quantity and the quality of the work will increase as a result of this change. We have so much potential that, with the help of the people and the environment around us, we are easily capable of putting a stop to animal cruelty. In the past, individuals frequently used lipstick made from natural ingredients to give themselves a unique appearance. The rainbow of colours that can be seen in nature comes from a variety of sources, including flowers, foliage, vegetation, and herbs. Natural cosmetics can be derived from a wide variety of plant parts, including grasses, flowers, foliage, and plants. Grass can even be found on flowers. It is possible to apply lipstick to one's cheeks using the leaves of certain types of flowers blossoms and the leaves of blossoms were frequently used by ancient people as part of their personal ornamentation. One of these is called kajal, and it is made from black coal that is acquired from the flame of fire. Traditionally, the eyes were decorated with this coal, which is known as kajal. Similarly, natural henna was utilized in the colouring process for both their hair and their nails. Natural henna was utilized to colour the hair and nails, and this process not only imparted colour but also lent freshness to the hair and nails. There is a significant amount of material present in nature that can be utilized by humans for the purpose of clothing and fashion without causing any damage to any living being. Only by coming together as a community, forming a united front, and educating those working in animal shelters, dairy farms, animal forestry, and other related fields will we be able to reach this stage and bring an end to this practice. In addition to clothing, we also use other materials such as cosmetics. Animal cruelty will no longer occur because of this, and whichever industries are currently operating under the guise of the clothing and fashion industries will have to be educated about it. This

will raise awareness not only among people but also among people's feelings of love toward animals. It will also raise awareness of the importance of each individual animal's role in the environment or ecosystem.

II. CONCLUSION

The conclusion is that animals and birds are subjected to cruel treatment, and the primary factor that contributes to the behaviour of those who engage in such treatment is a dearth of appropriate types of education and training about animals. Many individuals all over the world can collaborate and assist one another in the fight against cruelty to animals and birds. To my knowledge, it is not possible to lessen or eliminate the production of goods derived from animals; however, we can very easily eliminate such production for the sake of the environment and nature; in this regard, we can make use of human hair in addition to the resources provided by nature. It is said that to make any kind of change, the first thing that needs to change is ourselves. However, if we work together, we can put an end to animal cruelty in the name of the fashion and textile industries. All it takes is a little bit of collaboration, connecting people with each other, and providing information about animals and birds. Educating the parents, instructors, sanctuary foresters, zoo keepers, and others who participate in these cruel practices is the first step toward ending them.

REFERENCES

- [1]. <https://www.peta.org/issues/animals-used-for-clothing/>
- [2]. <https://www.worldanimalprotection.org.uk/blogs/fashion-industry-animal-cruelty>
- [3]. <https://www.four-paws.org/campaigns-topics/topics/animals-abused-for-fashion>
- [4]. <https://www.eurogroupforanimals.org/news/cruelty-out-fashion-report-exposes-treatment-wild-animals-exploited-fashion>
- [5]. <https://www.sustainably-chic.com/blog/animal-protection-in-fashion>
- [6]. <https://www.fourpawsusa.org/our-stories/press-releases/first-report-finds-fashion-industry-lagging-on-animal-welfare>
- [7]. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/306352693_Animal_Ethics_and_Welfare_in_the_Fashion_and_Lifestyle_Industries